

AUTO ASSISTIVE WHEELCHAIR FOR DISABLED PERSON

Jeet Adhikary¹, Ahona Chowdhury¹, Shishir Pal¹, Raktim Dutta¹

Susmita Das²

¹B. Tech Student

²Assistant Professor

Department of Electronics and Instrumentation Engineering

Narula Institute of Technology

81, Nilgunj Rd, Agarpara, Kolkata-700109

Corresponding author's email: jeetofficial2021@gmail.com

Abstract: A normal disabled person cannot do his daily work without the help of a third person. They have to depend on others to complete their daily needs, making their life harder. To fix this issue, we have proposed an auto-assistive wheelchair that will help disabled people do their tasks without taking the help of a third person. This wheelchair can be controlled by the disabled person by themselves using a joystick. This wheelchair will also have the feature of lifting them according to their convenient height for their work. The main feature of this wheelchair is that it will help disabled people in moving on staircases also which can usually be done by taking the help of others.

Keywords: self-balancing, smart wheelchair, actuator, rocker-bogie mechanism

1.0 Introduction:

In this paper, we have presented an auto-assistive wheelchair that will help disabled people in many ways. As we all know that a normal wheelchair helps disabled people in moving from one place to another with the help of a third person. But with the help of this prototype, a disabled person can move from place to place without taking someone's help. In this prototype, the disabled person can move using a joystick attached to the wheelchair. In this prototype, we have also taken the help of the actuator and hydraulic lifting mechanism. Using this mechanism, we will help the disabled person to balance while standing with the support of the wheelchair. The main use of this prototype is to help the disabled person to move on staircases without the help of a third person. For the function of moving on staircases, we have used the rocker-bogie mechanism in which we will be using a conveyor belt. Other than the conveyor belt, there will be extra pairs of wheels that will help the wheelchair to move on stairs. We have tried to make this prototype in such a way that it can be affordable for needy people.

2.0. Components used for the project:

1. Arduino microprocessor
2. Arduino Expansion Shield
3. 12 V Battery
4. Wheels
5. Jumper Wire

6. Acrylic sheets (for the complete structure)
7. Switch
8. Joystick
9. Actuator
10. microcontroller
11. conveyor belt
12. gyro sensor
13. proximity sensor
14. motor drivers
15. connecting wires
16. Seat Belt

3.0. Methodology:

3.1. Block Diagram of movement of wheelchair:

Figure 1: Block Diagram of wheelchair Movement

This is the block diagram of the movement of this wheelchair. Here we are using a 12V battery which will give power supply to the devices connected with it. Here the Arduino microcontroller will take input commands from the user through joystick control and then it will process the input and pass it to the motor driver which will control the movement of the wheels.

3.2. Circuit Diagram of movement of wheelchair:

3.2. Circuit diagram of the lifting mechanism:

Figure 2: Linear actuator

3.4. Block diagram of staircase climbing:

Figure 3: Block Diagram for the staircase motion

According to the above block diagram, a different switch is installed in the wheelchair for activating the conveyor belt movement on staircases. If the Arduino gets a signal from the switch, it will be processed and it will be sent to the motor drivers. Then the motors will be started and the conveyor belts will be moved during the movement of a wheelchair on the staircase, the upper body of the wheelchair will be static and only the lower body will function in this process followed by free movement.

Figure 4: Prototype Design

4.0. Results:

The project has been finished with success and utmost satisfaction. With the development of this project, we have learned a lot of new things and the problems a disabled person goes through every day. With the help of this project, we have tried to contribute our idea to the medical field and we hope that our contribution will positively help disabled people and we get some positive responses for our help to disabled people. This project also helped us to know about many new devices that can help make such projects. As we are using a small prototype, so according to the model it is rigid and strong .when the real-time prototype will be made by iron frame, it can take at least 70kg weight of a person. The height of the prototype from the ground level is 21cm. The total cost is 3000 rupees to make this prototype, for this prototype, it will be sold at 4000-5000 rupees cost. In the upcoming days, we will try to make this real-time wheelchair within 10000-20000 rupees cost.

5.0. Applications and Future Scope of the Project:

1. This wheelchair will help the disabled person to move by themselves via remote control.

2. This wheelchair will help disabled people to gain a convenient height according to their choice.

3. It will help them move on staircases without the risk of falling down and without the help of a third person.

4. We can install some safety features in it like an emergency number dialing system for their safety.

5. We have tried to make it cost-efficient so that it can be affordable for all categories of a disabled persons.

6.0. Conclusion:

To develop this project, we have learned to code the Arduino Microprocessor using Arduino IDE which is one of the most important and trending parts of modern coding. With the success of this project. We would like to continue our research work in this field and develop much more supportive and safe devices for disabled people. In the end, we would like to thank our mentor Ms. Susmita Das Madam for her great contribution to our project, without her this project wouldn't become a success.

References:

- Rc Simpson et al IEEE, Trans R ehabil eng, 1999 Dec, Automatic adaption in the Navchair Assistive Wheel Navigation system.
- Intro to sensors, pdf, how to use the sensors.
- Arduino, tutorial point simply learning, pdf, how to use the Arduino programing.
- ResearchGate, Development of an Autonomous wheelchair for the disabled and performance Analysis using ANFIS model, August 2020.
- Hesperian Health Guides," How to make Wheelchair parts".
- Div Portal, An optimization Design of the stair climbing Wheelchair, 2012,Belkinge Institute of Technology.
- Mechanical Design manual editorial board, 2007, Mechanical design manual machinery Industry press.
- ResearchGate, Modeling of a stairclimbing Wheelchair mechanism with high single step capability, IEEE xplore, M. J Lawn , Nagasaki University.
- Design and Modification of stair climbing wheelchair, 2018, International journal of Engineering Research & technology (IJERT).
- International Journal of Innovative Science an Research Technology, ISSN NO:-2456-2165, Automatic stair climbing wheelchair with bed, 2017.
- Control of a stair climbing wheelchair, M. abdul Ghani, Department of ACSE, University of Sheffield.